

CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO THE STUDY OF EMPLOYMENT MODELS

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Abstract

The article analyzes the trends arising in the modern process of employment, based on the nature and characteristics of world-class employment models that occurred during certain periods of socio-economic development. The study showed that the peculiar feature of a new employment model is based on the trend towards an increase in the number of people employed in the service sector due to the increase in the number of temporary workers.

Keywords: employment model, employment theory, post-industrial model, service coursework soda, nature of employment, grain from mednat, consumption rate.

It is important to thoroughly study the changes in the employment model that are in force in the labor market in ensuring the efficiency of employment, increasing the level of employment and managing the factors affecting it. In the conditions of modern development of the world economy, the employment model is changing under the influence of a number of global factors. The main feature of changes in the labor market during today's development is explained by the increasing growth of scientific and technical progress, which radically changes the structure and working conditions of the labor market, as well as the requirements for the qualifications of workers. Therefore, due to the main changes taking place in the economy, the importance of the evolution of the employment model and its analysis of the directions of development in the modern period is increasing.

To date, several theoretical and methodological approaches to the problems of employment and unemployment have been developed in the theory of Economics, each of which corresponds to a certain stage of periods of economic development in the world economy. One of the most famous of these theories is the classical theory of employment, which defines full employment of the population as a necessary condition for the existence of competition in the existing market, which is based on the fact that gross demand corresponds to gross supply [1, p. 73].

The basic principles of the classical theory of employment can go out of balance as a result of the intervention of the foreign market, which was based on an approach to improving the mechanism of the current free market activity. As factors contributing to its free development, wars, droughts, etc., which periodically arise in different regions of the world, causing imbalances in the economy, were considered. At the same time, the market mechanism has been interpreted as a self-regulatory mechanism that restores production and ensures a balance of income and expenses [2].

The new concept of employment theory was developed by J.Keynes published in his fundamental work "The general theory of Employment, Interest and money" [3], published in

1936. It shows a new conceptual approach to employment theory that completely rejects classical theory on the grounds that the mechanism of employment regulation is not specific to a market economy, and justifies the fact that the equilibrium of an economy is achieved through the regulatory role of the state. J.Keynes argues that the emergence of full employment of the population in a market economy is not an absolute coincidence, therefore, the capitalist economy cannot be a self-regulating system, this sphere requires constant regulation by the state. At the same time, he saw unemployment and inflation as a natural feature of capitalism that was dashed by state intervention by stimulating the funds of the population and the investments of entrepreneurs.

In the second half of the twentieth century, Keynes's employment model was replaced by the model of industrial society, the specifics of which are manifested in the following:

1. The industry, which is dominant in all sectors of the economy, has formed a technological injection.
2. In the main sector of the economy, the employment ratio has changed: the proportion of people employed in agriculture has decreased, and the proportion of employment in industries and services has grown.
3. Rapid development of the population of cities and towns took place.
4. At the global level, priority began to be given to the development of the general level of literacy and national education systems, which determine the qualitative aspects of employment.
5. The level of population consumption has increased significantly.
6. In the structure of total human costs, the cost of Labor time is reduced.
7. Changes in the demographic indicators in the development of society, including a decrease in the rate of birth and death, changes associated with an increase in life expectancy, are observed.

Based on the laws of development, at the end of the second half of the twentieth century, the model of industrial society began to turn into a post-industrial model. The change in models is largely determined by structural changes in the employment process, which depend on the growth of labor productivity and changes in the dynamics of demand in the field of material production. One of the main features of these changes is a decrease in the share of those who are busy in the industry with an increase in the level of material production. Thus, in developed countries, a decrease in industrial production and the share of workers employed in it occurs simultaneously with an increase in its total volume [4, p. 170]. These changes are associated with the process of modernization of production, and are replaced by computer and automated technologies, which, as a result of modernization, require less cost for labor costs, but require high-quality labor qualifications. At the same time, the need for modern technical services, carried out by enterprises outside the process, arises, and this partially transfers the production process to the service sector. Therefore, the modernization of production significantly reduces traditional production labor, while increasing the need for technical work related to the preparation and maintenance of production processes, as well as post-production service.

The rapid development of the service sector in the economic literature is considered as a condition for the employment process in this area. According to M.Porter, such changes in the employment process are due to a number of factors – the increase in the need for services, which is, its change, that is, the transfer of specific functions that serve production to

enterprises outside the enterprise. As a result, the demand for specialists involved is directed to the external labor market, which, in turn, ensures the minimization of the company's costs. M.Porter estimates that the proportion of the services involved in the final product or service in value added to up to 80% [5].

From the 80s of the last century, labor in the world began to differ in types of employment (main production or service). In this area, the role of high-tech services is growing, which leads to an increase in demand for skilled labor, which is distinguished as an independent type of business.

According to a number of economists [6], the development of the service sector in the late 90s was influenced by the law of the tightening of needs, the growth of the amount of intellectual resources and the long-term factors of economic development that arise with a change in the quality of human capital.

As a key factor in the formation of population employment, the necessary condition for their rapid development in the world economy is highly developed material production, since it is on this condition that conditions arise for the redistribution of workers in the field of services. The first to break into this trend is A.Toffler focused in the mid-60s of the last century, whose studies found that physical labor began to decline by more than 50% in the activities of the population of developed countries as a major change in the expenditure of Labor forms [7]. Among these factors that create the necessary conditions for the development of the service sector, the following can be included:

1. Structural needs of scientific and technical progress. These needs include services (information and communication services) arising from the need to develop high-tech production and introduce modern technologies into production. As a result, transport, finance, telecommunications services form the basis of the modern infrastructure of the economy and, at the same time, stimulate the creation of new jobs in other areas by forming a system of inter-sectoral relations.

2. Dynamics of the standard of living of the population. One of the factors of the rapid growth of the service sector in developed countries in the 60s of the last century was an increase in the well-being of the bulk of the population, which was associated with an increase in social labor productivity. Residents with more income were able to spend coarser money on additional services.

3. The transformation of Consumer Psychology in society. The second half of the twentieth century saw changes in consumer culture [8, pp. 36-37]. Also, the level of income of the population is being reevaluated, which, on the one hand, is reflected in the impact of increased income and its impact on the labor market, and on the other, leads to an expansion of the need for new services that replace their personal domestic activities with hired workers. The effect of income contributes to the formation of new life relationships, which leads to an increase in free time and, accordingly, the development of a need for rest and lifestyle improvements.

The expansion of the service sector ensures the demand for workers manifested in the following:

1. The increasing complexity of production and the increase in production for everyday life are accompanied by an increase in labor costs associated with the transmission of this product to the consumer.

2. The increased need for Education directly affects the process of formation of employees in accordance with the new requirements.

3. With the growth of income, the attitude of the population to their own health changes, which becomes a factor in the formation of human capital. Thanks to this, the process of developing health and medical services is rapidly expanding.

4. A significant improvement in quality of life has led to an increase in life expectancy in developed countries, which stimulates an increase in the volume of services such as the development of a wide range of social services, in particular, services for the elderly, the creation of wellness centers, the development of recreational services.

5. Growth in the number of busy women. In terms of complexity, opportunities have expanded for the employment of most women in the service sector, including those without special education and housewives.

6. An increase in the level of urbanization. These conditions ensure the development of new types of services associated with living in cities, including life security and other types of household services.

Thus, the conditions that ensure the rapid development of the economy of the service sector expand the demand for new workers, which in developed countries do not make certain changes to the industrial model of employment.

In addition, at the end of the twentieth century, there were significant changes in the system of human motivation for Labor. In the system of Labor motivation, material motivation moved to the second level, satisfaction with the work performed, the ability to show one's abilities, the possibility of self-improvement, etc. went to the first level.

Structural changes taking place in the economy increase labor flows under the influence of factors that increase the demand for labor resources in the service sector. In addition, the service sector forms new, highly efficient jobs focused on modern production and jobs related to direct service to the population.

The new model of employment is similar to the post-industrial model, in which the role of traditional factors of production changes, information and knowledge occupy a special place, the main development is focused on intellectual activity. In this model, a special place is occupied by the service sector, which includes the function of forming new, highly qualified jobs for production services and ties with the provision of services to the population, low-skilled jobs.

Within the framework of this model of employment, a different attitude towards the concept of "work" is formed. If, within the framework of the industrial society model, wages were paid in exchange for production activities, then in the post-industrial society it is included in those types of activities that are already effective, but not always paid. This is why the approach to employment is changing, since the official status of participation in social production is changing. After all, any legal activity that contributes to the growth of personal income can be explained in terms of employment.

Thus, the modern model of employment is characterized by the following specific main trends:

1. As the main trend of employment in developed countries, it can be shown that the composition of the economically active population moves from the sectors of material production to the service sector. At the end of the last century, in the US, one in six people in the national economy were engaged in the sectors of material production, while more than 70 percent worked in the services sector. In the European Union, however, one in five people

employed were employed in material production, while in Japan more than 63% of those employed in the post-2000 period moved into the service sector [9, pp. 31-32].

2. With the development of the service sector, the use of temporary hired workers is becoming more common. For this reason, the new model of employment is characterized by the expansion of the use of temporary labor. The number of people employed in the service sector, as well as the increase in the number of temporary workers, has influenced a decrease in the level of personnel reduction in sectors and industries and the activation of their mobility in the labor market.

3. Along with the above, there is another trend associated with the rapid development of the service sector - this is an increase in the proportion of women in the total composition of workers.

4. Depending on the level of labor intensity in the employment model, there is a division of workers into two groups: a group with low labor capacity, but high professional training of workers (telecommunications, computer technology, financial services, etc.); a group with high labor capacity and low requirements for the level of Professional Training (trade, catering, service, etc.).

5. According to the state of legality of Labor Relations, in the new employment model, employment forms in the form of formal and informal, as well as self-employment (own business, self-government) are distinguished.

The implementation of organizational and economic changes in the formation of the labor market in our country, where the process of formation of free market relations is taking place, based on the essence of the above-mentioned employment models, expands the possibility of accelerating the integration of the national labor market into the international labor market, managing factors affecting employment, as well as increasing.

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